

Civil Service Reforms in Kazakhstan and Its Influence on Modernization

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Abstract—Civil service (public administration) is an important social institution of society properties. Civil service institution had a significant impact on modernization processes in Kazakhstan through ensuring the functioning of all the subsystems of social life. This article is an attempt to analyze the reforms of public service institution in Kazakhstan and to assess its influence on modernization processes.

Keywords—Civil service, Kazakhstan, modernization, a national model of civil service, civil service reforms, bureaucracy.

I. INTRODUCTION

DURING 22 years of independence Kazakhstan has reached significant economic growth, which is achieved through implementation of state policy. In this case public service institution as an implementer of state policy that plays important role. From this perspective it is important to analyze public service reforms together with modernization processes. As a result of dynamic reform processes over the last 22 years, a national model of public service is formed with its own characteristics and peculiarities, which are due to system governance and socio-political structure of Kazakhstan.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Issues of public service reforms in different countries are considered by many authors. Study of Mulgan was dedicated to public service reforms in New Zealand [1]. Study on civil service sector reforms in Malaysia found that these reforms achieved limited results because of lack of reforms in political system [2].

Also reforms in South Asia are examined by other authors [3]. Study found that reforms had not achieved tasks of reforms due to following reasons: over-dependence of the political leadership on a permanent civil service; viewing administrative reform as the same as public sector reforms; lack of political commitment to implement reforms; refusal of the powerful bureaucracies to allow changes to the existing arrangements; inability of weak political institutions to persuade other institutions to comply with proposed reforms; and frequent change of governments which obstruct the gradual implementation of changes [3].

Reference [4] considered the role of e-government in public sector reform in Italy and Japan. The study found that the use of e-government initiative in Italian taxation system and procurement processes enhanced financial rationalization,

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transparency, better accountability and improved communication and management among local governments. In Japan the use of information communication technology helped to ensure better sharing of information between the central and local governments [4].

Reforms of civil service in Kazakhstan were investigated by Francis Amagoh and Shahjahan Bhuiyan. Authors considered public sector reform in Kazakhstan [5].

Also many researchers study certain aspect of development and formation of this institution. However, impact of the civil service institution on modernization processes was not studied. For developing countries as Kazakhstan it is important to identify impacts of their institutions on whole development of the country.

III. REFORMS IN PUBLIC SECTOR AND MODERNIZATION PROCESSES IN KAZAKHSTAN

In political science the term bureaucracy has a dual heritage. Max Weber argued that rational bureaucracy could more efficiently manage and coordinate activities of members of organization than organizational forms of management based on personal loyalty [6]. Whereas many authors consider that bureaucracy inhibits the development. In this connection we would like to analyze main changes in public sector with public sector reforms over more 20 years.

Reforms in the public service of Kazakhstan can be divided into two phases:

The first stage of reforms covered period from the beginning of 1990 to 2011 and current stage which is started from 2011 to present.

According to the Development Strategy until 2030 one of the long-term priorities was to create a professional state. Implementation of these goals in the creation of public service and a highly efficient management structure that is facing our country, largely driven by the professionalism of the civil servants.

Knox noted that according to the strategy for comprehensive administrative reform for development entitled “Kazakhstan- 2030: Prosperity, security and improved living standards for all Kazakhs” the following aims of administrative reforms were proposed:

- To increase the effectiveness of the government working collectively as a state organ and individually through the role of each minister.
- To implement modern information technology and eliminate bureaucracy in government bodies.
- To create an effective and optimal structure of state bodies.

- To restrict state interventions in the economy [7].

Also, in January 2007, a Presidential decree entitled 'Measures aimed at Modernizing the Public Administration System in the Republic of Kazakhstan', set out the main priorities of this sphere. Improvement of the quality of public administration processes, procedures and public service provision, professional skills, efficiency and coordination of the state bodies were main priorities according to this decree [8].

Following stage of the reforms began in 2011. In 2011 a Code of honor of civil servants was adopted. Public servants ethics is one of the most actual issues. The Code of honor of civil servants RK (the rules of ethics of public servants) is an official document, which defines the behavior of employees not only when performing their duties, but also outside of their professional activities.

In March 26, 2013, the Law of Kazakhstan "On amendments and additions to some legislative acts of the Civil Service" came into force. This law and other regulations were designed to ensure the selection of the most deserving personnel, their professional and career advancement because of recognition of merit. Henceforth, in the selection and promotion of cadres in the civil service principle of meritocracy (recognition of the merits) should work.

IV. NATIONAL MODEL OF CIVIL SERVICE

Conducting qualitative modernization of the machinery of government, above all, requires further deepening administrative reform, in particular the improvement of the civil service system.

Therefore, based on the need to further improve the efficiency of public administration, it seems appropriate to form an effective system of public services, adapted to the new realities and strategic objectives of the country, as the lag in further reforming the civil service system does not preclude significant inhibition of the modernization process in the future.

In the study of features public service institution, review of international experience is important.

Thus, in the legal structure of the public service and its administrative and legal regulation are the following models:

1. Romano-German model (career).
2. Anglo-Saxon model (positional).
3. State Service of Islamic Guidance.
4. Labor model.

"Career" model of Civil Service implements in France, Germany and Japan. Its main feature is benefits and guarantees in the civil service (social protection of civil servants, pension guarantees, stability status).

Admission to the public service occurs on competitive examinations based on the principle of equality of all the candidates. Mandatory conditions for admission are the availability of basic education and special preliminary training.

Public service is based on career development, which is the main principle of "dedication to the service of the state".

Level of payments in this model depends on the positions of

seniority and rank civil servant. In addition to these "deficiencies" with the CIS common point of view, there is another, that threatens the economy and the state in general - the lack of interdepartmental mobility officials that became one of the most acute problems of the career model.

"Positional" model is implemented in the U.S., UK and Canada. The main characteristic of the model is the emphasis on the concept of New Public Management (New public management) and a system of quality assessment and performance [9].

Kazakhstani model of Civil service in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Civil Service" in 1999 corresponds exactly to "positional" model of public service.

Features "Kazakhstani model" of Civil service (positional model), in accordance with the Law "On Civil Service" in 1999, as follows:

- division of government posts;
- political and administrative;
- protection of administrative employees at change;
- political head of the agency;
- competitive selection for admission to administrative civil service;
- job classification;
- model and departmental qualification requirements;
- new wage system;
- creation of the authorized body of the Civil Service.

The next stage of public service reform was the period from 2003 to 2007, including changes from November 11, 2003 and Presidential Decree 27 July 2007 № 372. This stage can be characterized as a transition to the position-career model.

Features of this model were:

- introduction of the appointment in order to transfer;
- introduction of the executive secretary;
- creation of disciplinary councils authorized body for the Civil Service.

Professionalization of the civil service system based on the principles of meritocracy, efficiency, effectiveness, transparency and accountability to society is an important factor in ensuring the competitiveness of public administration and the provision of quality public services.

In this regard, the Head of State gave new tasks to improve the national system of public service. Kazakhstan on the basis of world models and taking into account the best international practices developed its own model of public service.

The concept of a new model of public service provides a three-pronged objective, which provides:

- Effective personnel policies and human capital management in the public service;
- High quality of public service delivery and performance of public bodies;
- Improving ethics and reducing corruption.

In the implementation of the Concept of a new model of public service of Kazakhstan, a law was adopted in 2013. The law provides:

- Strengthening the principle of meritocracy in the selection

- and promotion of personnel;
- The creation of administrative body “A”;
- Improving the institutions and mechanisms of personnel management;
- Improving the status and authority of personnel services;
- Strengthening the disciplinary and ethical oversight, improving corporate culture [10].

Thus, it should be noted that to date, the national model of public service has formed a solid conceptual and legal framework. Adoption of a national model of public service based on global best practices and our own experience is designed to provide further modernization of Kazakhstan.

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

Today, it is clear that a modern legal and regulatory framework for the civil service has formed in Kazakhstan.

Also, vocational training system of state and municipal employees is being further developed. Organizational prerequisites are formed and mechanisms of interaction of state civil service and civil society institutions are further developed. The mechanisms of public service development program were developed. Mechanisms for combating corruption in the public service was established, formed and began operating mechanisms for evaluating the work of state bodies.

Cadre structure of the civil servants is following: Political servants consist of 4%, administrative servants consist of 96%.

Fig. 1 Administrative and political servants [11]

From a gender perspective public administration of Kazakhstan shows almost proportional to the ratio. So, 43% of public employees are men, 57% of civil servants– women [11].

Fig. 2 Number from Gender perspective [11]

Modernization of society in modern conditions is impossible without the gains of the entire structure of government. This system of government itself needs operational reform in the first place. All this raises the following issues: the state apparatus to take over as the main engine of reform and guarantor of their irreversibility, legal, material, financial and welfare of civil servants is closely connected with the formation of a strong budget, and this is one of the causes of corruption, high staff turnover, lack of incentive for professional development. Modern legal institution of civil service - a system of law that regulates relations emerging in the organization of the civil service, the status of civil servants, guarantees and procedures for its implementation, as well as the mechanism of the civil service.

In the Strategy “Kazakhstan – 2050” specific targets for the professionalization of the state apparatus are set out to improve staffing, the fight against corruption, to improve the quality of public services.

According to them, following further priorities was identified:

Introduction of Talent Management

According to the experience of leading countries is planned to introduce a mechanism to attract, and the effective use of employee retention, which can make a significant contribution to the development of the civil service.

Phased Transition to More Advanced Types of Testing

In order to further improve the quality of the civil service selection for the transition of testing knowledge of legislation to modern forms of exams such as competency tests, to the specific case studies, essay writing, etc.

Assessment of Competencies Managers on the Experience of the Corporate Sector and International Consulting Groups

The Academy of Public Administration will establish Project Management Center, Center for the Study of competencies (design competence profile civil servants) with the participation of international partners.

Currently, work is underway to develop a mechanism for determining the competence profile leadership positions studied international experience in this field.

A Clear Legal Separation of the Concepts of Corruption Offenses from Non- Professional Ethics

Taking into account international best practices proposed by the Agency in corruption offenses include acts punishable by criminal law. Disciplinary violations attributed to ethical transgressions maintaining existing sanctions.

Introduction of "Adviser on Ethics" institution

The main objective of this institution is seen in the prevention of the commission of ethics and corruption offenses, civil servants advising on anti-corruption legislation and ethics.

Creation of the Commission for Protection of Meritocracy

To enhance the protection of the principle of meritocracy in promoting the public service is supposed to create the Commission on the Protection of meritocracy, whose decisions will be binding on public administrators.

Implementation of the Risk Management System

Government bodies will work on a system of risk management in the quality control of public services, as well as ethical and disciplinary control. Taking into account international best practices will be developed for detection, identification, quantification, assessment and procedures to minimize risks in the government [12].

To conclude, Kazakhstani model of Civil Service is formed and it concludes all best practices of Civil Service.

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